

ENERGY RATING FOR EVALUATING PERFORMANCE OF PEROVSKITE AND PEROVSKITE-ON-SILICON TANDEM DEVICES IN REAL-WORLD CONDITIONS

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ABSTRACT: We present an independent analysis of expected real-world performance of single junction perovskite cells and tandem perovskite-on-silicon devices relative to single junction silicon cells. As energy-rating of perovskite devices is not yet realised and the technology is still rapidly maturing, this is a theoretical study. We create an “optimistic” scenario, which represents successful upscaling of current record-efficiency perovskite lab cells. Our model considers temperature, spectral, angular and junction mismatch effects. In this scenario, we find that single-junction perovskite cells perform better in many real-world climates than under standard test conditions; in one climate, the single junction perovskite cell has a higher absolute energy yield than a silicon cell that had 3 % higher efficiency under standard test conditions. For tandem cells, we find that tandem energy gains of between 29 % and 40 % are achieved when the band gap of the front cell is optimised to the climate. We also simulate less optimistic scenarios by reducing the performance of both the perovskite or silicon sub cells. We find that tandem energy gain is strongly affected by the initial choice of sub-cell efficiency, which largely explains the large variations in published modelling studies.

Keywords: see enclosed list of keywords

1 INTRODUCTION

Perovskite (Pk) cells, and particularly modules, are still an immature technology. The ultimate performance limits that will determine the levelized cost of energy (LCOE) produced are yet to be determined. For this reason, there are numerous publications exploring the theoretical and practical limits of power conversion efficiency (PCE) that might be achieved in mature devices [1] [2] [3] [4] in single and multi-junction configurations.

The figure of merit that really matters to applications, however, is the amount of energy that a device produces under real-world conditions. PCE is usually measured under a specific set of standard test conditions (STC) (1000 W m⁻², AM1.5G spectrum, 25 °C), but are strongly affected by changes in irradiance, spectrum, angle and especially temperature. In real-world conditions most PV modules operate for most of the time at lower efficiencies than predicted by standard test conditions. Performance ratio (PR) is often used to determine real-world performance relative to STC:

$$\eta_{real} = PR \cdot \eta_{STC} \quad (1)$$

where η_{real} is the average PCE achieved in real world conditions and η_{STC} is the PCE at STC. PR depends on a number of factors including climate, mounting, site, *etc.*. For traditional PV modules, PRs in the region of 80 % to 95 % are typical. In the case of two-terminal tandem devices optimised for STC performance, deviations from STC also introduce current-mismatch losses between the junctions, so even lower PRs may be expected.

Theoretical studies on the anticipated real-world performance of perovskite-on-silicon tandem PV devices [5] [6] [7] [8] have produced very different conclusions. The most optimistic predicts >30 % yield improvements for tandem devices compared to single-junction silicon, while other studies predict no gain at all. These stark differences arise from the choice of device parameters (efficiency of Pk and Si sub-cells), the choice of real-world conditions, and the model assumptions (*e.g.* effect of temperature).

This work aims to resolve these differences by performing a theoretical investigation of real-world performance that could be achieved in the near future with device parameters based on a progression of today’s performance trends. To remove bias from the choice of conditions and to reduce model variation, we use standard

energy rating instead of energy yield as the main performance metric. Energy rating is defined by new international standards [9]. It provides a modelling framework for comparing the estimated relative performance of different PV devices in a set of six representative standardised climates [10]. We apply this framework to model a range of device parameters, representing a continuum for a “optimistic” future performance of perovskite cells to more pessimistic possibilities.

The focus of this paper is on perovskite-monocrystalline silicon tandem devices, though we also present interesting results on single junction Pk devices.

2 METHODS

We use a simple model for each cell junction based on the Shockley-Queisser formulation with the introduction of additional resistive and non-ideal recombination loss mechanisms. Our model includes a ‘quality factor’ that allows us to vary the efficiency of devices from a maximum that corresponds to the best current full-sized silicon cells and record small-area perovskite cells respectively. The latter is chosen with the assumption that future upscaling and technology maturity can enable large-area perovskite cells without further efficiency loss. We refer to this as the “optimistic” scenario. The chosen parameters under standard test conditions (STC) are shown in Table I. We assume that perovskite layers are optically thick, which reduces angular-dependence of Pk absorption and requires band-gap tuning to balance junctions in two-terminal tandem devices. A more detailed description of the device model is given in Appendix: Model details. Degradation and device stability are not considered.

Table I: Device parameters from default “optimistic” perovskite and silicon cells used in the model before band gap optimisation.

STC performance	Short-circuit current (A m ⁻²)	Open-circuit voltage (V)	STC Efficiency (%)
Perovskite (1.56 eV)	249	1.14	21.5
Silicon	413	0.72	24.5

The model allows the band gap of the perovskite cell to be tuned across the range that can be reasonably accessed by tuning the material composition using mixed halides and cations. The model implicitly calculates the temperature coefficient of each cell in a method consistent with reference [11]. Perovskite cells also have a unique feature that the absorption spectrum is blue-shifted at higher temperatures, reducing the amount of light absorbed, which has interesting implications for junction matching. As shown in Figure 1, the derived temperature coefficient is dependent on the choice of band gap and the quality factor, but for all cases is more favorable for Pk cells than Si cells. The temperature coefficient is a very important factor in determining energy yields. As module temperatures can reach in excess of 60 °C, losses can be very significant. We believe that this is the first study that includes the effects of band-gap dependent perovskite temperature coefficients on energy yields.

We calculate the expected power output for each hour in a year for each of the six standard reference climates. This calculation includes calculating the module temperature using the method described in the IEC 61853-3 standard [9]. Spectral response and angular effects are calculated using a simple optical model (Lambert-Beer type plus reflections) with band-gap dependent absorption coefficients. For tandem devices, the spectrum incident on the back cell is dependent on the absorption in the front cell, which includes angular effects for both direct and diffuse light contributions. For each hour, current-voltage curves are simulated for each cell, and combined in the case of two-terminal tandem devices. For an entire year, the total energy yield at maximum power point is summed and used to calculate an average operating efficiency and PR for the climate.

Note that we perform calculations at the cell-level and do not take account of cell-mismatch and other losses at the module and string levels or other system effects thereby assuming that these are not dependent on choice of cell technology.

3 RESULTS

3.1 “Optimistic” scenario

The optimistic scenario demonstrates the cell performance that might be achieved with successful scale-up of current record efficiency devices. It also assumes seamless tuneability of perovskite and ignores the problem of open-circuit voltage loss from gap-state formation in mixed halides, which currently limits efficiency of wider band-gap perovskites [12]; the assumption is that solutions to this issue can be found.

Figure 1 Efficiency (blue) and temperature coefficient (red) of a modelled optimum-quality silicon cell (dots) and perovskite cell (curve) as a function of band gap.

Figure 1 shows the predicted variation of STC efficiency and PCE temperature coefficient as a function of perovskite band gap. For single-junction (1J) Pk cells, optimum band gap for STC efficiency is expected to peak at a band gap between 1.5 and 1.55 eV and declines as the band gap is increased, mainly due to reduced absorption. For smaller band gaps voltage losses from non-radiative recombination and series resistance dominate. While the efficiency is less than 1J Si, the temperature coefficient of 1J Pk is more favourable, and becomes even better as the band gap is increased. Based on this information alone, one would expect the performance of the 1J Si cell to fall below that of 1J Pk at very high temperatures (~90 °C).

Figure 2 shows efficiencies of tandem Pk-on-Si devices with both two-terminal (2J2T) and 4-terminal (2J4T) configurations under both STC and one example

Table II: Performance of different device configurations under each standard climate for the optimistic scenario.

Standard climate name	STC	Tropical	Subtropical	Subtropical	Temperate	Temperate	High elevation
		humid	arid	coastal	coastal	continental	
Average operating temperature (°C)	25.0	48.5	43.8	32.9	21.1	24.8	14.5
Average operating in-plane irradiance (W m ⁻²)	1000	596	746	644	446	555	729
Diffuse irradiance (%)	0.0	56.3	26.5	51.3	58.1	40.9	33.3
Single-junction Si efficiency (%) ¹	24.4	21.5	21.9	23.2	23.5	23.3	23.7
Single-junction Pk efficiency (%) ²	21.5	21.7	20.5	21.9	22.4	21.6	21.0
2J2T efficiency (%) ²	32.2	29.0	29.5	30.4	30.7	30.5	30.6
2J4T efficiency (%) ²	32.9	30.9	30.3	31.8	31.9	31.4	31.4
Optimum single-junction Pk bandgap (eV) ³	1.52	1.54	1.52	1.52	1.42	1.42	1.46
Optimised single-junction PK efficiency (%) ³	21.5	21.7	20.5	21.9	22.5	21.8	21.1
Optimum 2J2T Pk bandgap (eV) ³	1.74	1.80	1.76	1.78	1.78	1.76	1.76
Optimised 2J2T efficiency (%) ³	32.2	30.5	29.6	30.8	31.4	30.7	30.6
Optimum 2J4T Pk bandgap (eV) ³	1.92	1.90	1.90	1.90	1.88	1.86	1.92
Optimised 2J4T efficiency (%) ³	32.9	30.9	30.3	31.8	32.0	31.4	31.4

standard energy rating climate. In line with previous studies, we find that the optimum band gap for a Pk front-cell is about 1.75 eV for the 2J2T configuration and between 1.8 and 2.0 eV for 2J4T. In this example climate (subtropical arid) all devices perform slightly worse than under STC conditions due mainly to the high temperatures.

Figure 2 Predicted mean efficiency for different device configurations operating in the subtropical arid standard energy rating climate (solid lines) and STC (dashed lines).

Table II lists the performance of each type of device under all standard energy rating climates. The irradiance-weighted mean module temperature and mean irradiance for each climate are also shown. As expected, Si cells perform less well under all reference climates than under STC conditions. On the other hand, 1J Pk cells have a performance ratio greater than 100 % in 4 out of 6 climates. In the tropical humid climate, the extreme temperature and relatively blue spectrum favour Pk over Si so much that the average efficiency of the 1J Pk cell is higher than the 1J Si cell.

3.2 Optimising band gap by climate

Figure 3 shows the PR predicted for each type of device in the optimistic scenario when the Pk band gap has been optimised for each climate (see also Table II). For 1J Pk devices, the benefits of optimising band gap by climate is small, 0–0.2 % absolute efficiency, but for 2J2T devices, the benefit is as much as 1.5 % absolute efficiency in the hottest climate.

Figure 3 Performance ratio and average efficiency for the different device configurations using optimistic scenario parameters. The Pk band gap is tuned for each device to optimise the yield for each climate.

3.3 Less optimistic scenarios

Even for mature technologies, such as monocrystalline Si, there are a wide range of cell types and qualities available, and this is even more true for Pk devices. Therefore, we have investigated the effect of combining sub-optimal Pk and Si devices to create tandem devices. This is done in a simplistic manner by introducing step-wise changes in cell parameters for series, shunt resistance, non-radiative recombination rate and optical losses. The resulting current-voltage curves are shown in Figure 4. For each sub-optimal scenario, both the STC efficiency and yield in each reference climate can be calculated. Figure 5 shows how the predicted temperature coefficient gets worse in both Si and Pk cells as the quality is reduced. This results in lower PR for less optimised cells.

Figure 4 Current-voltage curves for sub-optimal 1J Pk and 1J Si devices as cell parameters are detuned.

Figure 5 Variation of temperature-coefficient predicted by the model as a function of STC efficiency as cell parameters are detuned from the optimistic scenario values.

The tandem energy gain (gain in energy yield) for a 2J2T device relative to 1J Si varies depending on the relative quality of the different sub cells. For example, when a poor-quality Pk front cell is added to a good-quality Si back cell, the resulting 2J2T device has a lower yield than the 1J Si device. By contrast, when a high-quality Pk front cell is added to a poor-quality Si back cell then yield gains of over 40 % can be achieved. This tandem energy gain is plotted for one reference climate as a function of front and back cell STC efficiencies in Figure 6. In each case, the

Figure 6 Tandem energy gain predicted for 2J2T devices relative to 1J Si for sub-optimal quality front and rear cells as a function of front and rear cell efficiency. The subtropical arid reference climate has been used in this case. The blue dashed line shows the optimistic scenario for Pk front cells.

This helps us to understand why predictions for tandem energy gain in the literature are so varied. For example, reference [5] uses a Pk front-cell efficiency of 22 % and a Si back-cell efficiency of 22.5 % to reach a gain of >30 %. Reference [6] uses efficiencies of 19.7 % and 26.7 % respectively and uses a small front-cell band gap. That reference finds almost no gain at all. Both results are consistent with our own findings.

4 CONCLUSIONS

Through the use of a generic model incorporating temperature, spectral, angular effects and non-linearity, we have predicted the potential real-world performance of perovskite single and tandem devices relative to single-

junction silicon devices. In an optimistic scenario, the performance ratio of perovskite single-junction devices is expected to be greater than 100 % for most reference climates. In a tropical humid climate, a single junction Pk device is expected to have a higher yield than a single-junction Si device even though the Si device has a higher efficiency under standard test conditions.

Exploring the effect of sub-optimal front and back cells in a tandem configuration, we were able to show that the tandem energy gain is strongly dependent on the chosen efficiency for the respective sub-cells. The wide spread of predicted tandem energy gains reported in the literature is mostly due to the choices of sub-cell parameters used as model inputs.

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APPENDIX: MODEL DETAILS

A.1 Device model

The DC output for each cell is determined using equivalent-circuit models to generate current-voltage curves. For two-terminal tandem cells, the current-voltage curves from each sub cell are summed in series. The equivalent circuit parameters are dependent on a set of fixed device parameters and the variables G_{eff} and T_{cell} , denoting effective irradiance and module/cell temperature respectively. These variables are evaluated for each hour of a one-year reference climate data set.

For silicon cells, we use the 5-parameter single diode model with temperature-dependent parameters according to the California Energy Commission 5-parameter model as implemented in NREL's SAM simulator [13]. For perovskite cells, the temperature-dependent behaviour is not yet well known, and so assumptions must be made. We have derived our own model, following the work of references [8] and [11]. Current density J in the absence of series and shunt resistance is given by the two-diode equation:

$$J = J_{r0} \left[\exp\left(\frac{eV}{k_B T}\right) - 1 \right] + J_{nr0} \left[\exp\left(\frac{eV}{n_{nr} k_B T}\right) - 1 \right] \quad (2)$$

where J_{r0} determines the amount of radiative recombination and J_{nr0} non-radiative and V is voltage, k_B is the Boltzmann constant and T is temperature. n_{nr} is the ideality factor for non-radiative recombination and J_G is the photogenerated current density determined from the devices spectral response and in-plane spectral irradiance. J_{r0} is temperature-dependent and determined from the optical model using detailed balance. For non-radiative recombination, we assume a power-law dependence on carrier densities n and p : $recombination \propto (np)^{1/n_{nr}}$, and therefore the diode prefactor is determined by the variation of intrinsic carrier density n_i with temperature giving:

$$J_{nr0} = J_{nr0,ref} \left(\frac{n_i}{n_{i,ref}} \right)^{\frac{2}{n_{nr}}} \quad (3)$$

$$= J_{nr0,ref} \left\{ \left(\frac{T}{T_{ref}} \right)^3 \exp \left[\frac{E_{G0}}{k_B T_{ref}} - \frac{E_G}{k_B T} \right] \right\}^{\frac{1}{n_{nr}}}$$

where $n_{i,ref}$ is the intrinsic carrier density at the reference temperature T_{ref} , and $J_{nr0,ref}$ is the value of J_{nr0} at reference temperature when the perovskite band gap is E_{G0} . The perovskite band gap E_G also varies with temperature according to

$$E_G = E_{G,ref} + 0.0003 \text{ [eV K}^{-1}] (T - T_{ref}) \quad (4)$$

where $E_{G,ref}$ is the band gap at reference temperature and the band-gap temperature coefficient is taken from [11] (which remains to be determined for different variants of Pk material). The band gap of the simulated perovskite is then tuned by adjusting the parameter $E_{G,ref}$. Unlike some other models, this model gives a temperature and band-gap dependent ratio between radiative and non-radiative recombination, albeit with several assumptions which need to be experimentally validated.

Series and shunt-resistance are added to the above current-voltage equations or completeness. Photocurrent and radiative recombination are determined from the cell external quantum efficiency (EQE), for which we use a very simple optical model. It is assumed that the perovskite layer is optically thick, and therefore that absorbance is close to 100 % for wavelengths above the band gap. The increase in near band-edge absorption of at shallow illumination angles due to increased optical path length is ignored in our model. The EQE for a cell is given by a very simple cut-on/ cut-off equation:

$$EQE = EQE_{max} \frac{1 + \exp\left[\frac{(\lambda - \lambda_{off})}{w_{off}}\right]}{1 + \exp\left[\frac{(\lambda_{on} - \lambda)}{w_{on}}\right]} \quad (5)$$

where λ is wavelength and the cut-off wavelength is determined by the band gap $\lambda_{off} = \frac{hc}{E_g}$, the cut-on wavelength λ_{on} is determined by parasitic absorption and w_{off} is determined by the Urbach energy $E_U = \frac{hc}{\lambda_{off}^2}$ (h is the Planck constant and c is the speed of light). EQE_{max} is the maximum EQE, which is slightly less than 100 % to represent parasitic absorption losses. The EQE for silicon uses the same equation with different parameters. In tandem devices a transmission loss of 5 % is assumed for all light passing from a Pk front cell to a Si back cell. An example of the resulting absorption spectra for a 2T device is shown in Figure 7. Additional angular-dependent reflection and transmission losses from a standard front-glass module encapsulation are added before conversion of light to photocurrent is calculated from the EQE and spectral irradiance. To determine cell temperature, we use the nominal operating cell temperature (NOCT) model described in [14].

Figure 7 Example EQE spectra for Pk front cell and Si

back cell respectively. The AM1.5 photon spectrum is also shown (black line) and current density is proportional to the red and blue shaded areas.

A.2 Default device parameters

The default device parameters for the optimistic scenario are shown in Table III. The rationale for choosing these values is as follows:

We aim to simulate a perovskite device that it may be possible to produce in moderate quantities in the near future (~5 years). To do this, we aimed to use model parameters suitable for current world-leading small-area cells and assume that these can be upscaled successfully with only a small increase in series resistance. To begin, we assumed a value of 1.5 for n_{nr} based on ref [15] (the results are not very sensitive to the exact value). The optical parameters are then chosen to match absorption cut-on and cut-off edges published in literature for high performance devices. We then fitted the remaining parameters $R_s, J_{nr0,ref}, EQE_{max}$ to match the published device characteristics (open-circuit voltage, short-circuit current, fill-factor) for a recent world-record small-area cell. To simulate upscaling, we added additional series resistance until the fill-factor matched that of the equivalent record 1 cm² cell. The latter is added because lateral series resistance in transparent conductors can be neglected in very small cells, but is present in larger cells. Above about 1 cm², busbars reduce the impact of further cell area increases. A similar procedure was used to obtain parameters for Si cells, but in this case we fitted parameters to the device characteristics of a world-record production cell.

Table III Default device parameters used in the “optimistic” model. *Values denoted with an asterisk are derated when simulating sub-optimal devices.

Symbol	Value	Description
<i>Perovskite cell</i>		
T_{ref}	298.15 K	
E_{G0}	1.49 eV	
$E_{G,ref}$	[1.42 – 2.0] eV	
n_{nr}	1.5	
R_s	0.5* mOhm m ⁻²	
R_{sh}	Infinite*	
$J_{nr0,ref}$	4.1×10^{-10} A m ⁻²	
EQE_{max}	0.954*	
E_U	16 meV	
λ_{on}	350 nm	
w_{on}	30 nm	
<i>Silicon cell</i>		
R_s	0.03* mOhm m ⁻²	
R_{sh}	20* Ohm m ⁻²	
α_{sc}	0.048 % K ⁻¹	
$J_{o,ref}$	9.87×10^{-10} A m ⁻²	
n	1.04	
EQE_{max}	0.99	
λ_{off}	1095 nm	
w_{off}	30 nm	
λ_{on}	360 nm	
w_{on}	35 nm	
<i>Device</i>		
T_{NOCT}	48.6 °C	